

The addition theorem of velocities

Harald Schröder

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According to Becker [1], exercise 10.3, p.305 in the special relativity theory it is valid for two velocity vectors $\vec{u}$ and $\vec{v}$:

$$\vec{u}' = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\vec{u}\vec{v}}{c^2}} \cdot \left[\vec{u} - \vec{v} + ((\vec{u} \times \vec{v}) \times \vec{v}) \cdot \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}{v^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

$\vec{u}'$ is the resultant velocity and $\vec{\beta} = \frac{\vec{v}}{c}$.

Now we transform the numerator with the expansion theorem of vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} & \vec{u} - \vec{v} + ((\vec{u} \times \vec{v}) \times \vec{v}) \cdot \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}{v^2} \\ &= \vec{u} - \vec{v} + ((\vec{u}\vec{v}) \cdot \vec{v} - v^2 \cdot \vec{u}) \cdot \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}{v^2} \\ &= \vec{u} - \vec{v} + \frac{(\vec{u}\vec{v}) \cdot \vec{v}}{v^2} \cdot (1 - \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}) - \vec{u} \cdot (1 - \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}) \\ &= \sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \cdot \vec{u} + \vec{v} \cdot \left[\frac{\vec{u}\vec{v}}{v^2} \cdot (1 - \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}) - 1 \right] \end{aligned}$$

We obtain:

$$\vec{u}' = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\vec{u}\vec{v}}{c^2}} \cdot \left\{ \sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \cdot \vec{u} + \vec{v} \cdot \left[\frac{\vec{u}\vec{v}}{v^2} \cdot (1 - \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}) - 1 \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

In this form the addition theorem is written in Schröder [3], chapter 3.5, equation (20), p.44.

Now we derive with equation (1) the special addition theorem. We choose $\vec{u} = (u, 0, 0)$ and $\vec{v} = (-v, 0, 0)$. It follows $\vec{u} \times \vec{v} = \vec{0}$ because of $\angle(\vec{u}, \vec{v}) = 180^\circ$. With that it is valid $\vec{u}' = (u', 0, 0)$ and we get:

$$u' = \frac{u + v}{1 + \frac{uv}{c^2}}$$

This is the known special relativistic addition theorem of velocities.

If $|\vec{v}|, |\vec{u}| \ll c$ and thus $|\vec{\beta}| \ll 1$, it follows:

$$1 - \sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \ll 1$$

Then we have with equation (1):

$$\vec{u}' \approx \vec{u} - \vec{v} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \vec{u} \approx \vec{u}' + \vec{v}$$

This is the usual classical case.

References

- [1] Becker/Sauter "Theorie der Elektrizität", volume 1, Teubner Verlag, Stuttgart, 21.edition 1973
- [2] Harald Schröder "Particular problems of special relativity theory", Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag, Berlin 2002
- [3] Ulrich Schröder "Spezielle Relativitätstheorie", Verlag Harri Deutsch, 2.edition, Frankfurt on the Main 1987